

2D SP₃ Neutron Transport Calculation Based on Particle Method

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ABSTRACT

In order to more easily treat a deformed geometry in the multi-physics simulation, we are developing a prototype code that applies the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method to the Simplified P₃ (SP₃) neutron transport calculation in reactor physics. When implementing the SP₃ calculation based on the SPH method (SPH-SP₃), the gradient correction method is used to reduce the SPH-discretization error. As a preliminary study, a simplified albedo boundary condition within the framework of SPH-SP₃ is used. To verify a prototype code of the SPH-SP₃ calculation for the two-dimensional xy geometry, the k_{eff} -eigenvalue was calculated for the TWIGL benchmark problem and compared with the reference value using MOC. Consequently, we confirmed that the numerical result of k_{eff} using SPH-SP₃ calculation with the gradient correction method agreed well with the reference MOC calculation, and the bias of k_{eff} between SPH-SP₃ and MOC could be reduced as the particle size in the SPH method became smaller. The kinetics calculation based on SPH-SP₃ was also tested for the ramp perturbation in the TWIGL benchmark.

Keywords: Particle method, Smoothed-particle hydrodynamics, SP₃, Gradient correction

1. INTRODUCTION

This study investigates a neutron transport calculation method that is applicable to a multi-physics simulation, which can more easily treat deformed geometry. For this purpose, we aim to apply the particle method [1–6] to the Simplified P₃ (SP₃) neutron transport calculation method [7,8].

The multi-physics simulation in reactor physics is one of the important research topics in order to carry out the reactivity insertion analysis and to estimate the risk of exceeding the criticality state in a transient situation, such as the progression of a severe accident in a nuclear reactor. For example, the previous studies used the particle method-based fluid calculation [9,10] for coupling analyses for hypothetical events where the fuel debris fell into the water during the retrieval operation. In the previous coupling calculations, the geometry data in the particle method were converted into those of the Monte Carlo neutron transport code MVP [11] to evaluate the effective neutron multiplication factor k_{eff} . Here, in order to achieve a practical multi-physics simulation, we consider that there are two key issues to be addressed: One is data conversion error in calculation geometry (e.g., spatial distributions of macroscopic nuclear cross section); the other is the high computational cost of the continuous energy Monte Carlo code.

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To address the above-mentioned issues, our previous study [12] investigated the development of a prototype code based on the neutron diffusion calculation code using the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method [1,2]. The SPH method is also applicable to the heat conduction equation, which is expressed by the 2nd-order spatial differential equation and is similar to the neutron diffusion equation. Through our preliminary study for a deformed fuel geometry in water [12], we could confirm the applicability of the SPH method to the neutron diffusion calculation, although there was room for improvement to reduce systematic errors due to (i) the SPH-discretization and (ii) the diffusion approximation. The purpose of this study is to develop the SP₃ neutron transport calculation method with the gradient correction method in the SPH discretization [5,6]. Note that a more detailed investigation on the usefulness of the gradient correction method is presented in another paper by co-author [13]. By focusing on the similarity of the SP₃ neutron transport equation to the heat conduction and neutron diffusion equations, we try applying the SPH method to the SP₃ neutron transport calculation. Here, the treatment of the boundary condition is an open issue because of the complexity in the SP₃ neutron transport equation. As a preliminary study, a simplified treatment for the albedo boundary condition was tested in the SPH-based SP₃ neutron transport calculation (SPH-SP₃).

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 briefly explains the numerical theory of SPH-SP₃. In Section 3, we verify a prototype code of SPH-SP₃ for the two-dimensional TWIGL benchmark problem [14] in the steady state. We also present a preliminary result of the kinetic analysis for the TWIGL benchmark using SPH-SP₃ with the on-the-fly POD kinetic calculation [15,16].

2. NUMERICAL THEORY

2.1. SP₃ Neutron Transport Equation

In the SP₃ neutron transport equation [7,8], the k_{eff} -eigenvalue equation with two neutron energy groups is described as follows:

$$-\nabla \cdot (D_g \nabla \phi_{0,g}) - 2\nabla \cdot (D_g \nabla \phi_{2,g}) + \Sigma_{t,g} \phi_{0,g} = Q_{0,g}, \quad (1)$$

$$-\frac{2}{5} \nabla \cdot (D_g \nabla \phi_{0,g}) - \frac{11}{7} \nabla \cdot (D_g \nabla \phi_{2,g}) + \Sigma_{\text{tr},g} \phi_{2,g} = 0, \quad (2)$$

$$Q_{0,g} \equiv \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^2 \nu \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{0,g'} + \sum_{g'=1}^2 \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{0,g'}, \quad (3)$$

where $\phi_{0,g}$ and $\phi_{2,g}$ represent the total neutron flux and the 2nd-order flux moment, respectively; $\Sigma_{\text{tr},g} = 1/(3D_g)$ is the macroscopic transport cross section; $Q_{0,g}$ is the fission and scattering neutron sources; the subscript g indicates the neutron energy group; and other symbols have conventional meanings in reactor physics. In Eqs. (1) and (2), the approximation of $\Sigma_{t,g} - \Sigma_{\text{tr},g} \approx \Sigma_{s1,g} \approx \Sigma_{s2,g} \approx \Sigma_{s3,g}$ is applied for simplicity.

2.2. SPH-discretization

Based on a similar way to our previous study [12], the Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH) method is applied to the SP₃ equations. In the SPH method, a flexible geometry is discretized by placing N representative points (or virtual particles) according to the shape. Each particle has representative

quantities at the spatial point, e.g., macroscopic cross sections $\Sigma_{x,g,i}$, neutron flux $\phi_{0,g,i}$, flux moment $\phi_{2,g,i}$, and volume V_i at the i th particle position \mathbf{r}_i . Then, macroscopic nuclear reaction rate $\Sigma_{x,g}\phi_g$ at the i th particle is approximated by summing the contributions of the j th neighbor particles:

$$\langle \Sigma_{x,g}\phi_{0,g} \rangle_i^{\text{SPH}} \approx \int_V W_h(|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}'|) \Sigma_{x,g} \phi_{0,g}(\mathbf{r}') dV' \approx \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|) \Sigma_{x,g,j} \phi_{0,g,j}}{\sum_{j=1}^N V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}, \quad (4)$$

where $W_h(r)$ means the kernel function. In this study, we used the following Wendland quintic kernel function [3] for the two-dimensional xy geometry:

$$W_h(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{7}{\pi h^2} \left(1 - \frac{r}{h}\right)^4 \left(1 + 4\frac{r}{h}\right) & \text{if } r < h \\ 0 & \text{else,} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

where h is the smoothing length. In the SPH-discretization of Eq. (4), the kernel function is corrected by the denominator $\sum_{j=1}^N V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)$ so that the integral over all space is equal to unity [5,6]:

$$\int_0^\infty W_h(r) 2\pi r dr \approx \int_V W_h(|\mathbf{r}_i - \mathbf{r}'|) dV' \approx \frac{\sum_{j=1}^N V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{\sum_{j=1}^N V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)} = 1. \quad (6)$$

As shown in Eqs. (1) and (2), the leakage term in the SP₃ equation is expressed by the divergence of the product of D_g and the gradient of $\phi_{m,g}$. Using a similar way as the SPH method for the heat conduction calculation [4], the following approximation is applied to the leakage term:

$$\langle -\nabla D_g \nabla \phi_{m,g} \rangle_i^{\text{SPH}} = -2 \sum_{j=1}^N V_j \bar{D}_{g,ij} (\phi_{m,g,j} - \phi_{m,g,i}) \frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|^2}, \quad (7)$$

$$\bar{D}_{g,ij} \equiv \frac{2D_{g,i}D_{g,j}}{D_{g,i} + D_{g,j}}, \quad (8)$$

where $\bar{D}_{g,ij}$ is the harmonic average of the two diffusion coefficients for the i th and j th particles [4]. In Eq. (7), the scalar-valued term $\frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|^2}$ is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \cdot \nabla_i W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|)}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|^2} = \frac{(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i) \mathbf{L}_i^{-1}(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)^\top}{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|^2} \left(-\frac{1}{r} \frac{dW_h}{dr} \Big|_{r=|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|} \right) \quad (9)$$

where the superscript \top means the transpose, i.e., the row vector $(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)^\top$ is the transposed column vector $(\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i)$; the derivative term $-\frac{1}{r} \frac{dW_h}{dr}$ is analytically solved and calculated as follows when using the Wendland quintic kernel function:

$$-\frac{1}{r} \frac{dW_h}{dr} \Big|_{r=|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|} = \begin{cases} \frac{140}{\pi h^4} \left(1 - \frac{|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|}{h}\right)^3 & \text{if } |\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i| < h \\ 0 & \text{else;} \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

\mathbf{L}_i^{-1} is the correction matrix for the gradient operator in the SPH-discretization. In the case of the two-dimensional xy geometry, \mathbf{L}_i^{-1} is calculated by an inverse matrix for the following matrix [5,6]:

$$\mathbf{L}_i = \sum_{j=1}^N V_j \left(-\frac{1}{r} \frac{dW_h}{dr} \Big|_{r=|r_j-r_i|} \right) \begin{pmatrix} (x_j - x_i)^2 & (x_j - x_i)(y_j - y_i) \\ (y_j - y_i)(x_j - x_i) & (y_j - y_i)^2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

2.3. Treatment of Boundary Condition

In the SPH method, the “wall particle” is typically used to express the Dirichlet boundary condition. Here, the j th wall particle has fixed values so that $\phi_{0,g,j} = \phi_{2,g,j} = 0$. In this study, the albedo boundary condition is assumed by giving the following diffusion coefficient for the wall particle:

$$D_{g,j} = \frac{R}{4} \frac{1 - \alpha}{1 + \alpha}, \quad (12)$$

where α is the albedo value and R is the particle diameter. Based on Eqs. (8) and (12), $\bar{D}_{g,ij}$ can be given to evaluate the leakage term toward the outer boundary:

$$\bar{D}_{g,ij} \equiv \frac{2D_{g,i} \frac{R}{4} (1 - \alpha)}{D_{g,i} (1 + \alpha) + \frac{R}{4} (1 - \alpha)}. \quad (13)$$

For example, $\bar{D}_{g,ij}$ is equal to 0 (i.e., no leakage) for the reflective boundary ($\alpha = 1$) and equal to $2D_{g,i}$ for the zero-flux boundary ($\alpha \rightarrow -1$). Note that Eq. (12) is a simplified treatment, which is empirically determined based on our preliminary study for the SPH-based diffusion code. Therefore, a more accurate treatment of the SPH-SP₃ boundary condition is an open issue at this moment.

As supplementary information, the reflective boundary conditions can also be given by the calculation condition without wall particles toward the direction of the reflective boundary.

2.4. k_{eff} -eigenvalue Calculation by Wielandt Iteration

Consequently, the k_{eff} -eigenvalue equation of Eqs. (1)–(3) can be expressed by a matrix-vector equation. In this study, the Wielandt iteration [17] is used as the outer iteration solver to efficiently solve the fundamental eigenvalue k_{eff} and the corresponding eigenvector $\boldsymbol{\phi}$:

$$\left(\mathbf{A} - \frac{1}{k'} \mathbf{F} \right) \boldsymbol{\phi} = \left(\frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} - \frac{1}{k'} \right) \mathbf{F} \boldsymbol{\phi}, \quad (14)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\phi}$ is the column vector of neutron flux moments, and the size is equal to $4N = (\text{number of particles } N) \times (\text{number of energy groups } 2) \times (\text{number of flux moments } 2)$; $\mathbf{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{4N \times 4N}$ and $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{4N \times 4N}$ are annihilation and production matrices, respectively; k' is an estimate, which should be slightly larger than the fundamental eigenvalue k_{eff} . Since SPH-SP₃ is the mesh-free solver, a typical iterative solver with the CMFD acceleration cannot be applied to efficiently solve the simultaneous equations of SPH-SP₃. Therefore, in our prototype code of SPH-SP₃ using C++/eigen 3.4 [18], the direct method of the sparse LU factorization is used to solve the sparse linear system of Eq. (14) at each outer iteration. As the smoothing length h increases, the matrices of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{F} become dense. Therefore, the SPH-SP₃

calculation requires more computational costs than the SP₃ calculation using the conventional finite volume method.

3. VERIFICATION

3.1. Calculation Conditions

We developed a prototype code of SPH-SP₃ based on the numerical theory as explained in Section 2. To verify our prototype code, the TWIGL benchmark problem [14] was numerically solved. As the preliminary results of the TWIGL benchmark problem, this study presents the numerical results of k_{eff} -eigenvalues before and after the perturbation, where the values of $\Sigma_{a,2}$ for the perturbed region are 0.1500 and 0.1465 cm⁻¹ before and after the perturbation, respectively.

Figure 1. Top view of TWIGL benchmark (particle diameter $R=2$ cm).

In the SPH-SP₃ calculation, the particle diameter R was changed from 8 to 0.25 cm to investigate the discretization error. The Wendland quintic kernel function [3] with the smoothing length $h = 2R$ was used. Figure 1 shows the top view of the calculational geometry in the SPH-SP₃ calculation with $R = 2$ cm. To simulate the zero-flux boundary, the diffusion coefficient of the wall particle was set as $D_g = 10^{15}$ cm instead of $+\infty$. The reflective boundary was given by the condition without a particle at the left and lower boundaries. To investigate the impact of the gradient correction method, we also carried out the SPH-SP₃ calculation without the correction, i.e., the kernel correction factor $\sum_{j=1}^N V_j W_h(|\mathbf{r}_j - \mathbf{r}_i|) = 1$ in the denominator of Eq. (4) and the correction matrix $\mathbf{L}_i^{-1} = \mathbf{I}$ (identity matrix) in Eq. (9). The reference values were obtained by MOC with the linear source approximation [19,20]. The flux region was discretized by the spatial mesh in 0.5 cm×0.5 cm units. The macroscopic transport cross section $\Sigma_{\text{tr},g}$ was given by $\Sigma_{\text{tr},g} = 1/(3D_g)$, and the self-scattering cross section $\Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow g}$ was corrected to satisfy $\Sigma_{\text{tr},g} = \Sigma_{a,g} + \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow 1} + \Sigma_{s,g \rightarrow 2}$. The zero-flux boundary condition was given by the albedo value of $\alpha = -1$.

3.2. Criticality Analysis

Table I summarizes the numerical results of k_{eff} -eigenvalue by the SPH-SP₃ and reference MOC calculations. Figure 2 shows the numerical results of $\phi_{0,g,j}$ and $\phi_{2,g,j}$ by the SPH-SP₃ calculation with the gradient correction and $R = 2$ cm. If the gradient correction method was not used, the systematic bias of k_{eff} between the SPH-SP₃ and the reference value was ~400 pcm. Thanks to the gradient

correction method, the k_{eff} results by the SPH method agreed well with the reference values, and the systematic bias decreased as the particle diameter R became smaller. Note that the bias reduction dependence with respect to R seemed to be low, because our implemented SPH method had the 1st-order accuracy of the Taylor series expansion after SPH discretization [6]. To further improve the calculation accuracy of SPH-SP₃, the implementation of the SPH method with the 2nd-order accuracy [6] may be necessary.

Table I. Numerical results of criticality-eigenvalue by SPH-SP₃ calculation.

particle diameter R (cm)	before perturbation				after perturbation			
	SP ₃ without ∇ correction		SP ₃ with ∇ correction		SP ₃ without ∇ correction		SP ₃ with ∇ correction	
	k_{eff}	bias (pcm)	k_{eff}	bias (pcm)	k_{eff}	bias (pcm)	k_{eff}	bias (pcm)
8	0.91703	355	0.91350	-32	0.92073	371	0.91752	21
4	0.91704	355	0.91367	-14	0.92067	365	0.91743	11
2	0.91709	361	0.91376	-3	0.92070	368	0.91740	9
1	0.91711	363	0.91379	0	0.92070	368	0.91737	6
0.5	0.91711	362	0.91379	0	0.92069	367	0.91735	3
0.25	0.91710	362	0.91379	0	0.92068	366	0.91733	1
reference	0.91379				0.91732			

Figure 2. Numerical results of neutron flux moments (particle diameter $R=2$ cm, after perturbation).

3.3. Preliminary Result of Kinetic Calculation

Figure 3 presents the preliminary result of the ramp perturbation case in the TWIGL benchmark problem. The kinetic calculation of SPH-SP₃ was carried out by the on-the-fly POD kinetic calculation [15,16]. Namely, the kinetic calculation using the fully implicit method with the coarse time step $\Delta t_c = 0.1$ s was performed to generate the POD bases from two ϕ vectors at the start and end points at each time interval of Δt_c in the on-the-fly manner. After that, between each of coarse time interval of 0.1 s, the POD kinetics calculation was carried out using two POD bases with the fine time step $\Delta t_f = 0.001$ s. Consequently, we could confirm that the variation of total power by the SPH-SP₃ calculation was nearly equal to that of the reference MOC calculation using the Multigrid Amplitude Function (MAF) method [20]. A slight difference in total power between the SPH-SP₃ and reference calculations was observed; thus, further investigation on the error source is a future research topic.

Figure 3. Preliminary result of ramp perturbation (particle diameter $R=0.25$ cm).

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study clarifies that the gradient correction method is crucial to accurately calculate the k_{eff} -eigenvalue using SPH-SP₃ with the gradient correction method. Although our prototype code of SPH-SP₃ was verified through the simple TWIGL benchmark, future research topics are further verification and validation (V&V) for a three-dimensional deformed geometry, and the multi-physics simulation coupling with the SPH-based fluid and heat conduction analyses.

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